

Research Article

Companion in Motherhood: How MomMe Embraces the Journey with Grace

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Abstract: Welcoming a child is a cherished milestone for married couples, yet it ushers in numerous challenges, particularly for new mothers. The transition to motherhood can be overwhelming, marked by uncertainties and the need for reliable guidance. Recognizing this pressing concern, the innovative MomMe application emerges as a comprehensive solution, aiming to ease the challenges faced by mothers of all experience levels. Derived from "Mom" and "Me," symbolizing its focus on guiding mothers through the journey of parenthood, MomMe is ready to provide assistance in childcare. One significant issue that MomMe addresses is the prevalence of the 'Baby Blues' phenomenon among new mothers, a condition characterized by feelings of sadness, anxiety, or depression following childbirth. By offering tutorials on essential topics such as confinement care and newborn essentials, MomMe equips mothers with practical knowledge and support. Moreover, the application seamlessly connects mothers to nearby care centres and fosters a nationwide network, enabling them to share tips, seek advice, and support one another through the ups and downs of motherhood. MomMe serves as a beacon of hope for mothers struggling with postpartum emotional challenges, promoting mental well-being and resilience. Beyond its immediate impact on maternal health and well-being, MomMe holds vast commercialization potential. With its unique features and holistic approach, MomMe taps into the ever-growing market of parenting applications, offering a valuable resource for modern families. Its innovative solutions and user-friendly interface position MomMe as a leader in the parenting landscape, promising both societal benefits and commercial success. As the demand for digital parenting solutions continues to rise, MomMe stands at the forefront, poised to make a significant impact on the lives of mothers and families worldwide.

Keywords: confinement mother; maternal health; parenting application.

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1. INTRODUCTION

It is imperative that all women who have recently given birth take into consideration the importance of preparation following childbirth (Isa, A. M., 2023). It is critical to take the correct steps after giving birth in order to properly care for the kid as well as one's overall health and physical body. Thus, the MomMe app serves as a helpful resource, particularly for first-time mothers who lack prior experience or expertise of caring for a child.

MomMe is a helpful resource for wives and husbands who require appropriate counsel, as it is specifically developed to offer guidance and easily accessible information. The app emphasizes Health & Wellness within the tourism sector, encompassing baby care through various methods such as Malay Tradition, Chinese Method, or Indian Method. A period of convalescence following childbirth, known as confinement and lasting around 1 month, continues to be observed in these three traditional cultures (Naser et al., 2012). The convenience of finding childcare centres, contacting postnatal midwives, or locating massage places for mothers and babies nearby provides parents with essential support. This also directly boosts the local economy as the app helps promote local businesses by creating job opportunities. The application not only focuses on end-users, namely parents and babies, but also on the local community involved in the medical, health and wellness industry.

This application is developed to assist travellers who are expecting but still wish to travel. It offers comprehensive information about the best locations for services and treatments related to mothers and babies, including clinics, hospitals, and mother-and-child clinics. Apart from treatment locations, MomMe also offers helpful advice regarding each pregnant mother's journey, including a variety of guides, safety instructions, and references. By using this application, expectant mothers can plan their trip in a more organized and safe manner without having to worry about the needs of the mother and child. MomMe is a useful application or tool that helps expectant travellers make sure their trip is safe, comfortable, and easy.

Figure 1 showcases the MomMe logo, a powerful symbol that represents the essence and uniqueness of our apps. This logo represents our brand's commitment to providing elegance and courage to mothers throughout their journey with grace and strength. Its design embraces the nurturing, caring, and empowering characteristics that constitute the MomMe experience. As a recognizable emblem, it speaks to our target audience, inspiring trust and confidence in the quality and purpose of our offering.

Figure 1. MomMe Logo.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Parenting entails significant responsibility, as early childcare profoundly influences a baby's development. Fundamentally, children require essential care that encompasses both emotional and physiological safeguards to meet standard expectations for growth and physical development, including adherence to guidelines for healthy weight and administration of recommended vaccinations (Institute of Medicine and National Research Council, 2015). For new mothers, the lack of experience in infant care is a common challenge. Although they may seek guidance from relatives or friends with parenting experience, such advice might not provide complete and comprehensive support.

Furthermore, existing resources and platforms for parental guidance may lack cultural relevance and inclusivity, especially in regions where diverse traditions and practices prevail. This gap in support services can result in heightened stress and uncertainty among new parents, potentially affecting the well-being and development of both the parent and the child. Certainly, research by Muscat et al. (2014) indicates that stringent maternal expectations regarding infant regulation can compound feeding and sleeping issues in infants, potentially exacerbating postpartum depressive symptoms.

The absence of apps that not only offer guidance and support to parents is seen as an opportunity to create a comprehensive parenting guide app that not only focuses on parents but also opens business opportunities in the in health and wellness tourism. Through the MomMe application, businesses such as massage centres and postnatal health centres can promote their services more rapidly.

Addressing the need for comprehensive and culturally relevant parenting support services is essential for promoting positive maternal and child health outcomes, enhancing parent-child bonding, and fostering healthy family dynamics. By empowering first-time mothers with the knowledge and resources they need to provide optimal care for their infants, well-being and resilience within families and communities can be promoted while also improving the health and wellness tourism business opportunities.

3. OBJECTIVES

MomMe, a confinement mom app can be a very helpful resource for empowering and encouraging young parents especially new mothers during the crucial postpartum phase. It can boost their self-esteem, well-being, and capacity to take care of both themselves and their babies. The MomMe app innovation is created to achieve the following objectives:

1. To provide mothers convenient access to tools and information at anytime and anywhere.
2. To assist mothers in keeping an eye on themselves and their baby's health and welfare.
3. To offer more personalized and applicable experience by focusing suggestions and guidance on the mother's unique needs and preferences.
4. To build a community support where mothers can exchange ideas, offer guidance, and show encouragement.
5. To offer local communities job opportunities by facilitating the features of discovering nearby local businesses that can be a help to mothers and infants during postpartum and boost local communities' economic performance.

4. NOVELTY & ORIGINALITY

Despite the abundance of material regarding postnatal planning on social media, MomMe provides more cutting-edge features, including guidance within the programme, to assist in treating or caring for moms who have recently given birth. Following appropriate practices can promote both physical and emotional well-being after childbirth. Postpartum confinement is a convalescence period with various lifestyle restrictions lasting about one month after childbirth (Naser et al., 2012). Additionally, MomMe is specifically designed to assist with planning and meeting the needs of both mothers and babies. Its unique approach involves providing a selection of nutrient-rich foods crucial for postpartum recuperation. Studies have shown a significant association between unfavourable

confinement experiences and postpartum depression (PPD) (Paliwal et al., 2023), underlining the importance of dietary considerations and offering precise recommendations on beneficial and detrimental food choices.

One of the standout features of MomMe is its comprehensive food preparation menu and recipes, tailored to the confinement period. From traditional recipes passed down through generations to innovative culinary creations, MomMe offers a diverse array of options to suit every palate and preference. Recognizing the importance of cultural and religious traditions during this time, MomMe offers a curated selection of 44-day confinement meal plans for first-time mothers, accompanied by easy-to-follow recipes and instructional videos. Whether it is adhering to dietary restrictions or honouring cultural practices, MomMe ensures that mothers have the support they need to navigate the postpartum period with confidence and grace.

This application extends its potential by providing comprehensive video tutorials aimed at guiding mothers in preparing balanced and nutritious meals for their babies. Its features a menu tailored to a one-year-old baby and above, suggesting foods and vitamins that are appropriate for the child's growth and development. In addition to offering mothers guidance, this app goes above and beyond by offering a budget-friendly checklist of baby necessities. MomMe also offers crucial and practical details regarding the kinds of baby products, like formula milk, diapers, and baby-safe wind oil.

Discover the MomMe app, your ultimate companion in navigating the beautiful journey of motherhood. Not only does it provide invaluable advice on prayers and dhikr to soothe the newborn's sleep troubles, but it also aligns with Islamic teachings, ensuring your baby's peaceful rest with the recitation of a *Surah*. With a comprehensive collection of lullaby songs curated specifically for babies, MomMe ensures a serene environment for infants to drift into a restful slumber. Whether it's calming melodies or heartfelt prayers, this app encompasses all the essentials for nurturing your child's well-being.

The MomMe application is also created with the purpose of enabling users to store vital documents for later use. The MomMe application is designed to help users conveniently store and access vital documents whenever needed. This app is particularly beneficial for mothers, allowing them to keep essential health record and treatment plans such as infant immunization logs and doctor appointments. These immunization records are crucial for parents planning to pursue further education or work abroad, as well as for enrolling their children in first grade. By centralizing these important documents, MomMe simplifies the process of managing and retrieving necessary information, ensuring that parents are always prepared and can be access whenever needed. The MomMe application also offers storage for pictures and videos, enabling mothers to preserve and relive their sweet journey and memories in a digital album of their baby.

Not to mention, the app offers rebates for every baby's care purchase receipts. For each eligible receipt uploaded, mothers earn points based on the total amount spent. The more receipts they upload; the more points they accumulate. Points are then credited to the user's account and can be viewed within the app's dashboard. Once a certain threshold of points is reached, mothers can redeem their points for rebates or discounts on future purchases, including childcare centre cost.

MomMe partners with a variety of retailers and brands to offer exclusive deals and discounts, allowing mothers to save money on essential items for themselves and their families. A further benefit of MomMe is that it can link to other services, like baby care, massage services, or those that are reliable and always in accordance with their budget and desired service type. This makes it easier for mothers to follow through on their abstinence plans, whether they are daily or 44-day packages because postpartum confinement is a convalescence period with various lifestyle restrictions lasting about one

month after childbirth (Naser et al., 2012). MomMe also has a location-based connection with a variety of confinement services providers; reservations can be made through the MomMe application.

Another aspect of MomMe's novelty lies in its emphasis on community engagement and peer support. This app offers community support by providing group chat features connecting mothers from all over the country. Care providers pay a special attention to psychological aspects of mothers' health as well as physical aspects and they try to make a positive and safe childbirth experience for mothers and their newborns by more social support (Zamani 2019).

This feature facilitates user interaction within the MomMe platform, enabling them to engage in discussions, share insights, provide support to new mothers, discuss their personal experiences and their babies' development, and seek advice on navigating daily challenges. Pregnant women need social support from their friends, health professionals and family members especially their partners, to have mental and psychological balance. This MomMe can serve as a space for them to share stories while abstaining and caring for the child. It can also serve as a support system for other women who are going through difficult times. By fostering a sense of solidarity among mothers, MomMe creates a supportive ecosystem where women can share experiences, exchange advice, and form lasting friendships.

5. METHODS USING MOMME APPLICATION

When it comes to postpartum recovery and adjusting to parenting, using a confinement application can be helpful because it can be quite hard and complicated especially for new mothers to keep track of their health as well as their baby. Table 1 provides a generic how-to tutorial for using the MomMe application.

Table 1. MomMe Application Utilization Steps

<p>Step 1: Users are required to download and install the apps from Google Play or App Store.</p>	<p>Step 7: Many features can be selected such as meal planner, treatment packages, education, medicines, specific business information based on the location, immunization record, doctor's appointment, video and photo digital album, choices of lullabies and others.</p>
<p>Step 2: Create a new account and fill in required information for new users.</p>	<p>Step 8: Users can key in doctor appointments and record vaccination schedules for infants.</p>
<p>Step 3: Log in by entering the email or phone number and passwords of the users.</p>	<p>Step 9: Pictures, receipts, or documents regarding the baby can be scanned, captured, and kept in the app.</p>

<p>Step 4: Select preferred language and set your location.</p>	<p>Step 10: Users can join community support group chat to communicate with other mothers.</p>
<p>Step 5: Users can choose their religion before proceeding, as an optional step.</p>	<p>Step 11: Users can click FAQ section for more information or ask in the chat box that will directly be replied with bot.</p>
<p>Step 6: Users will be directed to the home page of their selected religion.</p>	<p>Step 12: Users can provide feedback to improve the app and enhance the user experience.</p>

6. SOCIETAL BENEFITS

In Malaysia the experience of pregnancy and childbirth is often followed by sadness, fear, anxiety, and difficulty making decisions (Lye, 2011). According to Wang et al., (2023) Postpartum depression (PPD) refers to a set of mood disorders characterized by persistent depression occurring in mothers within 4 weeks postpartum. An estimated incidence of PPD ranges between 14 % and 25 % (Ozcan et al., 2017; Shorey et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2021b), and it is as high as 34 % during the COVID-19 epidemic (Chen et al., 2022). It has been reported (Anderson et al., 2017) that 18 % of these patients have suicidal thoughts. PPD not only affects the maternal emotions, but also causes a series of combined effects (Pouyan et al., 2019), shedding light on the prevalence and impact of mental health challenges during the postpartum period. MomMe, the comprehensive confinement period planner app, offers societal benefits that extend far beyond individual convenience addressing this matter. Firstly, MomMe helps to address societal challenges related to maternal mental health. The app offers resources for coping with the emotional and psychological aspects of motherhood, reducing the stigma surrounding postpartum depression and anxiety. Underscoring the importance of considering sociocultural contexts in understanding and addressing postpartum mental health challenges.

Additionally, by providing guidance and support to first-time mothers, MomMe contributes to the overall well-being of families. When mothers feel supported and equipped with knowledge about caring for themselves and their infants during the crucial postpartum period, they are better able to provide attentive care, fostering healthy development for their babies.

Enhancing family development is a priority. Additionally, MomMe encourages well-informed decision-making regarding healthcare practices and parenting choices in the parent community. By providing evidence-based information and tools for tracking maternal and infant health, the app empowers mothers to advocate for their own well-being and their babies. This leads to more engaged and proactive healthcare behaviours, ultimately reducing healthcare costs associated with preventable complications. Furthermore, MomMe fosters community engagement and support networks among mothers. Mustafa's anthropological perspective on postpartum depression emphasizes the importance of social support in maternal well-being (Mustafa et al., 2014). Through features such as community support, the app facilitates connections between mothers facing similar challenges and experiences. These virtual communities provide opportunities for mutual support, knowledge sharing, and promoting a sense of belonging. Not to mention, the benefit it brings to the economic angle by providing job opportunities to local communities with a feature of discovering nearby local businesses that can be a help to mothers and infants.

Overall, MomMe not only assists individual mothers in navigating the challenges of early motherhood but also contributes to building stronger, healthier families and well economically communities. By promoting maternal well-being, reducing stigma, empowering informed decision-making, and fostering social connections, MomMe serves as a valuable resource for societal advancement in the realm of maternal and infant health.

7. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, MomMe stands as a beacon of support and empowerment for first-time mothers, offering a holistic approach to navigating the challenges of the confinement period and early motherhood. By providing access to valuable resources, evidence-based information, and a supportive community network, MomMe not only enhances the well-being of individual mothers and their infants but also fosters societal benefits that ripple outward. Through its focus on promoting maternal mental health, informed decision-making, and community engagement, MomMe contributes to building stronger families and communities. As a mobile app developer, creating MomMe is not just about developing a convenient tool; it is about making a meaningful difference in the lives of mothers and their families, ultimately shaping a healthier and more supportive society for generations to come.

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